

Semiotic systemity of visual artworks: Case study of *The Holy Trinity* by Rublev

GEORGIJ YU. SOMOV

Postprint* v1.0

*Somov, G. (2007). Semiotic systemity of visual artworks: Case study of The Holy Trinity by Rublev. *Semiotica*, 2007(166), pp. 105-180. Retrieved 6 Oct. 2017, from doi:10.1515/SEM.2007.055

Abstract

The systemity of visual artworks can be described by the interrelation of several semiotic models as: (a) interrelations between verbal and non-verbal systemities; (b) interrelations of the three semiotic aspects, both internal ones and those with the three semiotic aspects of artwork verbal basis; (c) signs formed by codes, systems of linguistic type, text, and context; (d) sign form including denotations, connotations, and organizing structures, and finally, (e) sign system of individual elements and details. The Holy Trinity painted by Rublev illustrates developed interrelations of these models.

1. Introduction

It is possible to examine separate levels, denotations, connotations, sign units, and structures of visual artworks. I have already tried to substantiate some of these semiotic objects (Somov 2005, 2006). It is also important to have in mind a general semiotic systemity of visual artworks. The models of theoretical semiotics help to understand this. The models themselves can be interrelated and specified better based on the studies of semiotic systemity of artworks. The masterpieces of visual art ideally correspond to this goal. The specificity of creation, influence, and cultural destiny of *The Holy Trinity* by A. Rublev (figure 1) are analyzed below in detail. Special attention is paid to this icon and is explained by its specific features. The researchers pointed to an extraordinary effect of its perception. *The Trinity* fascinates a spectator who cannot take his eyes off and admires for a long time, being plunged into contemplation and rest, feeling harmony and appeasement. In connection with this, the explorers of the icon talked about its special melodiousness, luminosity,

Figure 1. *Andrey Rublev, 'The Holy Trinity' (1422–1427, State Tretyakov Gallery, Moscow)*

and aristocraticism of forms. These and other features of *The Trinity* are interrelated in its semiotic systemity. Earlier, I have tried to demonstrate some signs forming an artwork. In the present article, relying upon the results of different studies and observations and my own analysis, I shall try to demonstrate what the systemity of visual artwork is, using *The Holy Trinity* as an example.

2. Verbal and nonverbal; Three types of semiotic systemities of the icon

The perception of visual artworks always represents the interrelations of visual sign formations proper with verbal systems and signs of other channels of information production (tactile, acoustic, and others). *By the character of information production, the three types of semiotic systemities are distinguished: (1) visual semiotic systemity proper, (2) verbal semiotic systemity, and (3) non-visual sensor semiotic systemity.* These three types of systemities form the integral semiotic systemity of visual artwork. If we regard theoretically the three distinguished semiotic systemities within the sign model by Peirce, we can formulate that (1) can be regarded as sign or representamen, (2) as interpretant, and (3) as object. On the other hand, (3) can become representamen, (1) object, and (2) interpretant. The three systemities can be quite independent and developed. The icon by Rublev is an apparent example of this. *The interrelation between the visual systemity proper (1) and verbal semiotic systemity (2) is especially apparent in visual artworks having a developed basis in linguistic texts of culture.* These are, for example, medieval Christian works based on New Testament subjects. Images of the Trinity are characterized by multiple specific features of interrelations with various commentaries of angelophany to Abraham accepted in Christian culture. The icon by Rublev is based on the concept of Holy Trinity developed in the Church of Moscow in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries. A complicated verbal systemity of this concept is built in the icon, evolving to the systemities of visual sign formations proper. Usually, in the processes of work perception (information production), visually differentiated representamens acquire the character of signs, being related to visual objects, verbal sign systems, and sign systems of other (nonvisual) channels of communication. In the processes of the creation of conceptual works of visual art (e.g., *The Holy Trinity*), visual sign systems are, vice versa, formed under the influence of verbal factors. The major relations of concept are developed in visual denotations: difference of Trinity hypostases, their dialog meaning the blessing of sacrifice, and the agreement to offer it up. The basic elements of concept of Trinity (sacrifice, unity, and the tripersonality of God) also are included in major visual connotations. *Interrelations of proper visual (1) and non-visual sensor semiotic systemity (3) of artwork are based on the correlation among the signs of channels of production of sensor information.* These interrelations can be strengthened by the interrelations between (a) denoted objects of non-visual and sensor character and (b) these objects and the objects of visual sign systems. The interrelations of this kind are developed and strengthened in the analyzed work. Investigators often pointed to the feature of Rublev's paintings: developed

interrelations between images and sounds, painting and musical nature, feelings of slight movement and rest. 'Figures of Rublev's works are monolithic, the pattern is polysemantic, the coloring is restrained. The fluidity of linear organization and mild color gradations produce an impression of quite regularity, light movement without any sharp transitions. This causes the feeling of silence and rest' (Laurina 1989: 112).¹ *Interrelations of verbal (2) and non-visual sensor semiotic systemity (3)* relate verbal description of events and emotive meanings of sensor information. In visual art, these interrelations can be revealed and strengthened. Silence and rest forming important states of *The Holy Trinity* by Rublev are related directly to the ideas of harmony and unity of the verbal concept of the icon. The general semiotic systemity of visual artworks becomes more visible in the differentiation of denoted systemities. This systemity is specified on the fundament of three semiotic aspects.

3. Three aspects of the icon and their interrelations

In the model by Peirce, the sign presupposes the relations of its three sides: relation to an interpretant (interpreter), or *pragmatics*; relation to an object (reality), or *semantics*; and interrelations among signs, or *syntactics* (Morris 1971 [1946]). Semiotic scientists (Cherry 1952; Sebeok 1999, and others) proved that definite relations and systems were formed in each of these aspects in all semiotic systems. In connections with this, the model of three aspects in semiotic systems of visual art needs to be substantiated and specified. They appear in a specific way in a verbal systemity and systemity of an artwork as a whole. In the icon analyzed, the verbal basis has a developed character.

The pragmatics of verbal basis of the work consists in the way of interrelation between the doctrine of Trinity and historical events, goals, values, and religious convictions of people of a given epoch. The time when Rublev lived was the period of civil discord, the infancy of Moscow State, its liberation from the Tatar yoke, consolidation of peoples under the leadership of Christian Church. A prominent role in the integration of Russian people belonged to St. Sergius of Radonezh. St. Sergius preached for the Holy Trinity, which, in human consciousness, symbolized the idea of love mystery, fraternity, and unity of people. The doctrine led to the reconciliation, concord, and solidarity. The Church inspired warriors to the battle with oppressors. It was St. Sergius who blessed the Duke Dmitri Donskoi and his army before their important victory over the Golden Horde. St. Sergius founded the monastery devoted to the Holy Trinity. The monk Epiphanius the Wise wrote: 'Reverend

Sergius settled the temple of the Holy Trinity as a mirror for the congregation; looking at the Holy Trinity, they should overcome the fear of division ruling in this world' (S. Golubtsov 1981: 32). The icon was painted as the ideological center of the Troitse-Sergiev Monastery, which was reinforced by reverend Nikon, the disciple of St. Sergius (Vzdornov 1989). The investigators note that St. Sergius of Radonezh influenced the icon by Rublev via his disciple Nikon (Vzdornov 1989; S. Golubtsov 1972). Like the foundation of the monastery, the icon confirmed the ideas of St. Sergius.

The semantics of verbal basis of the icon is revealed when analyzing the evolution of the idea of Trinity. There are several theological exegeses of the episode of angelophany to Abraham. In the first centennials of Christianity, literal understanding of Bible text prevailed. This is why the wanderers were depicted wingless (e.g., frescos of the fourth and fifth centuries in the temples of Ravenna, Sicily, and Greece). Gradually, the interpretation of text grew deeper. At first, the predominating idea was the theophany of Christ and two Angels to Abraham. Then the episode was interpreted as the appearance of three Angels. This corresponded to the doctrine of fundamental triads by St. Augustine. St. Aphanasius, St. Ambrose, and other church fathers interpreted the image of three wanderers the theophany of the Holy Trinity. The God appears in three hypostases: God the Father, God the Son, and God the Holy Spirit. This idea was incarnated in Byzantine art. The depiction of this episode obtained the character of metonymy. The wanderers were perceived as Angels who, in their turn, represented the tripersonality of God. This system was developed by St. Sergius. Before him, the predominating interpretation of this Bible episode was the theophany of Christ and two Angels. This is why the image of Christ was in the center (figure 2). In the epoch of St. Sergius, this interpretation was rejected as heretical; an attempt was made, using a traditional basis, to inspire mildly the idea of Trinity (Vzdornov 1989). The dialog of three Persons of Trinity and related idea of uniting God's love was brought to the forefront. The moment of Christ's agreement to sacrifice Himself for the salvation of humankind united the idea of Trinity and self-giving love. Researchers examining *The Trinity* interpreted this episode in details: 'The moment is visualized when one of God hypostases expresses readiness to martyr Himself for the salvation of mankind' (Alpatov 1972: 98). 'The Trinity is represented as the Pre-existent Council, by the decision of which the Divine Economy, or way of humankind salvation by the sacrificial death of Christ, was initiated. God the Father addresses to the Son and sends Him to the world, while the Son expresses the readiness for the sacrifice blessed by the co-action of the Holy Spirit' (N. Golubtsov 1960: 35).

Figure 2. 'The Holy Trinity.' Icon painted ca. 1230. Plate on western gates of the Cathedral of Nativity of the Mother of God, Suzdal. Christ is in the center, with Angels on each side. This composition was declared heretical in the fourteenth century

The main verbal concept favored the formation of three realities, forming the metonymy of the icon: wanderers' repast on the background of Mambre oakery and Abraham's mansion; Angels, and the Triune God making an important decision. In connection with this, all objects and environment also obtain the character of metonymy. The table is the place where the decision of crucial significance for the world is rendered. The cup given to the wanderers by Abraham is a Communion Cup and symbolizes the sacrifice. The seats become symbols of thrones, while their pediments denote the basis of universe.

The syntactics of verbal basis of the icon is developed as interrelations of Divine Persons. The relations among hypostases of Trinity are expressed via sign systems of their dialog (poses, gestures, and mutual inclinations) and visual substance (signs of colors, directions, configurations, contours, etc.).

The three aspects of visual basis are implemented visually in the three aspects of the icon as a whole. *Icon pragmatics* relates it with major interpretants — human aspirations, value systems, prevailing ideology, and goals of communication. Therefore, the most important effect (significance) of the work by Rublev is undoubtedly the meaning of love and concord, which is intrinsic to the ideas of St. Sergius. This major meaning of Rublev's icon was clearly determined by Pavel Florensky, a known theologian of early twentieth century: 'Human culture, represented as a chamber, world of life represented as a tree, and earth represented as a rock — all this is small and worthless, as compared to this communication of inexhaustible and infinite love; everything is only around it and for it, because, via its blue color, music of its beauty, its existence above sex, age, and all terrestrial determinations and detachments, it is the Heaven itself, the absolute reality, the absolutely best, which is above all' (Florensky 1989: 53). Love and concord are felt by a person as the main value of his life. This meaning is developed in specific sign systems. Mutual inclinations of silhouettes, mild counter-movements, tranquillity of poses and gestures, interrelations between head movements and Angel's looks, peace and rest, organic interrelations of color configurations and contours, and other sign formations create the basic meaning of the icon. *Semantics of the icon* is based on the indication and expression of various realities. (This interpretation deviates from the determination of semantics as the domain of meanings accepted in linguistic and semiotic concepts and is closer to the semiotic theory by Morris). Sign systems of the visual level are related to different realities, such as: visual perception of the environment, texts and concepts of culture, and the gnostic sphere of the human psychic world. Semantics of visual artworks includes: (1) realities of depicted objects

(believability of objects and their properties, representation of human interrelations, feelings, and characters); (2) meanings of life situations, and (3) realities formed in the verbal sphere of culture (half-real or imaginary heroes and events). The semantics (3) can be divided along two lines: (3a) models of the world and (3b) cultural meanings of modeled situations: mythological episodes or subject. In Mediaeval Christian art, predominating realities are those of exegetics referred to as verbal systems (3). Realities of depicted objects in Rublev's works reflect the verbal picture of the world and episode concept; they condition the visual semantics proper. According to the concept of Trinity, the triunity penetrates the whole world. This gave rise to the representation of the general picture of the universe on the icon. The thrones and their common pediment form its physical firmament. Energies of life move in the center. Celestial spheres of spirit are represented above. The fragments of the icon denote separate spaces of the world. In each of them, its own life pulses. Their own movements, forces, and energies are denoted. The representation of the universe in the *Trinity* by Rublev was marked by Alpatov. This representation is supported when the analysis of connotations is made. Realities denoted on the icon are seen to be multi-layered and form different domains of its semantics. *Icon syntactics* represents sign interrelations in its general semiotic systemity. It mainly organizes the interrelations among sign sides (among designates, signs proper, representamens, and signals). This aspect is well-pronounced. The aristocraticism of *Trinity* forms, which has been extensively discussed, represents refined interrelations along all sign 'cross-sections' and their sides (icons, symbols, connotations, relations of sign groups, representamens, and signals). This organization partly follows the traditional sign systems of the Trinity. At the same time, in this icon, the traditional construction was developed in new unusual means: reflection of tripersonality in various triadic structures, ornamental color configurations, melodiousness of interflowing lines, etc.

Different aspects of visual artwork are implemented in its meanings. In pragmatics, the relations linking an artwork with consolidating intentions, values, goals, and ideas are developed. In semantics, the relations linking an artwork with different realities are formed. In syntactics, the organization of sign structures is created, providing the production of information, and the work become convincing. Correspondingly, the *effect is manifested in three aspects*: (1) consolidating value systems, feelings, and ideas; (2) meanings of episodes, represented objects, objects of culture, and other denoted realities; and (3) emotional feeling of the general architecture of the work. This corresponds to three types of meanings, by Lemke: *orientational (1), representative (2), and organizational*

(3) (1983). In the integration of these meaning types, a united integrative effect of an artwork is formed.

4. Implementations of signs

All processes of perception and creation of a visual artwork are based on signs. *Signs are implemented in the structure of communicative situation* where the *mechanisms of language codes and systems of text and context* are involved (Jakobson 1971).

Codes represent mechanisms in which signs are incarnated (Chandler 1994). The formation (encoding) of an artwork relies upon codes, which are embodied in the process of perception (decoding). All codes implemented in the process of perception of visual artworks are based on fundamental codes — mechanisms of production of sensor information (Somjen 1972). Earlier, I have tried to demonstrate that there are *intentional codes* (danger, attractiveness, threat, compassion, and others) (Somov 1985a), *codes of object character, or identificational codes* (information about object boundaries, distances, movements, structures, etc.), and *organizational codes* (structures of signals, signs, and information ‘pieces’) (Somov 2006, in press a). Cultural codes are formed on the basis of natural ones (Chandler 1994). Interrelations of code sides form plans of expression and content according to Hjelmslev (Chandler 1994). Structures and characteristics of representamens become stable in the interrelations with objects (2), interpretants (1), and representamens (3). This is why the structures and characteristics of this kind actively develop in visual artworks. Their groups corresponding to the three types of codes are noticeable in artworks. The icon analyzed is an example of an active development of three groups of characteristics. Mild, mutually enveloping lines and forms, closed configurations, predominating light ochre color sites, dashed, gently flowing, and shivering contours are included in intentional codes and form emotional status. Circles of nimbi, repeating the contours of a cup, and S-shaped characteristics of Angels’ wings correspond to indentificational codes and promote the interpretation of object icons, indices of movements, and gestures. United organizing configurations, axes, and centers, straight lines joining various elements, proportional sections, rhythms, and symmetries form the basis of implementation of organizing codes and integrate the groups of relations and elements. In the unity of structures and relations, *visual integrities of relations and elements* are formed, by differential characteristics of three types of codes. They resemble the integrities distinguished by semiotic scientists in verbal systems (Sapir 1930). These integrities promote the activation

of definite characteristics in the interrelations with different types of codes, i.e., implementation of signs. For example, in *The Trinity*, the characteristics of circles strengthen the representaments of important signs. Clear circles of Angels' heads and nimbi contribute to the interpretation of larger and less definite circles denoting circular movements of the universe and energy flows. The contours of a cup are repeated in large configurations and contours. This reinforces the significance of the cup as an important sign of unity and triadic character of the universe. Triangles show through large constructions and contours. Integral groups of triangles are formed supporting triadic constructions. The features of this kind strengthen denotations, form connotations, and make the artwork more organized from the viewpoint of structure. Natural codes evolve into cultural codes and signs; in particular, the transition from the perception of three-dimensional space to a two-dimensional picture forms specific codes (Deregowski 1980; Altman 1992: 28–29). Simultaneously, the invariants of the perception of three-dimensional space are preserved (perspectives of objects of different plans are formed by differences in color and line thickness and picture diminution), as well as the inverse geometric perspective (structures of object changes at different distances). In icon painting, the codes of this type became specific under the effect of conditional character of representation of space and time. The events distant in time and space are painted together (Florensky 1994). Conditional codes are based mainly on the distinction and identification of episodes and personages and expression of their concepts. Conditional codes were elaborated as 'sets of methods known by users of environment within a broad cultural structure' (Fiske 1989: 312–316). *Languages* materialize and complement codes at a more concrete level. This becomes apparent when modeling the systemities of culture (Sonesson 1989, 1993). Languages of visual cultures, directions, genres, and styles of visual art are more concrete, relative to codes, as they are specified under the effect of sign systems of culture. In visual artworks of Christian culture, these are Bible texts, text-generated signs, and concepts of biblical episodes. On this basis, conditional representations of characters, objects, and their spatial and temporal relations emerged (Uspensky 1976; Raushenbah 1975, 1994: 181). The conventionality was enhanced by the need in strong emotional effect. The use of intentional codes required the organization of color signals predominating on a plane. This led to the utilization of local color configurations and generalized contours and lines. Conditional signs were merged with intentional-expressive signs and various connotations. Color and geometric generalizations contributed to the memorizing of form. The images of Angels, Mother of God, saints, and symbolic objects on icons and frescos became stable units and were included in the

identification of signs of Christian culture. On the icon by Rublev, these are configurations of Angels' wings, nimbi, white shrouds, and cup configurations. *The text* also conditions the incarnation of signs. In Rublev's *Trinity*, verbal texts of the Bible and its exegesis effect visual sign formation via several levels of texts. The concept of the episode (angelophany to Abraham) and the doctrine of Trinity determine the manner of representing Angels, their mutual allocation, poses, and gestures. The text of these interrelations determines different visual elements: color ratios, configurations, contours, etc. Systemities of some texts become here plans of expression of others. In general, the sign form, with its different denotations, connotations, and sign organizations specifies each individual sign. *The context* of visual artwork represents its environment. In the paintings like *The Trinity*, it represents the unity of process (tradition) and sign systems of religious cult. First of all, this is the site where the icon initially was placed: the way from the main gates of Troitse-Sergiev Monastery to the grave of St. Sergius, near the Cathedral of Trinity (Vzdornov 1989). The location required the dedication of the icon as the center and its interrelations with the environment as architectural sign systems. *The Trinity* was placed in a specific niche and came forth from the architectural environment. It is also typical that the icon board is a rectangle proportional to major elements of architectural ensemble, with the side ratio of 10:12.24, which was also typical for ancient Russian proportional systems (Barbyshev and Somov 1990; Titz 1994). There are some other relations with architecture, which will be examined below in connotation analysis. In general, the icon was included in the systemity of environment. A communicative situation of an important center was created on the way of people.

Interrelations of codes, plans, and signs are reflected in the levels of sign systems. These levels have multiple descriptions in the models of 'stratification type' of semiotic concepts (Prieto 1964, and others). The experience of analysis of visual artworks allows us to postulate that the most fundamental elements of this domain are *groups of levels of construction, integration, and organization* (besides them, there are some other groups). *The levels of construction* are apparent in visual artworks as *semantic units and relations, signs, representamens, and signals* (Somov 2005, in press b). These levels are formed regularly due to code-sign mechanism and the stratification of plans of expression and content. The plan of expression, being the 'ground floor' of fundamental codes of production of sensor information, forms sign representamens. The plan of content is organized into an independent level of semantic systems. The level of signs binds both plans. The level of signals is outcropped into independent relations and elements because of the need in structural organization

of differences and equities of plans of expression (Somov 1985b). This is why semiotic scientists soundly distinguish the signals as a specific level (Eco 1976; Sharov 1999). The level of signals generates visual art phenomena, which are known as ‘formal compositional regularities,’ ‘unity of sensitive material,’ and ‘decorativeness.’ In Eastern Christian visual art, these regularities were especially pronounced and relied upon the idea of direct effect of color and forms, which was mentioned by Ioann of Damask, Pseudo-Dionysius Areopagite, and others. Correspondingly, the forms became an independent powerful channel of impression. This Byzantine tradition is specially stressed by the authors examining *The Trinity* (S. Golubtsov 1972, 1981; Lasarev 1997). This is why some of them seriously affirm that *The Trinity* by Rublev corresponds to Byzantine theory of art in the most complete way (Alpatov 1974). The *levels of integration* of semiotic systems realize the interrelations along the direction from structure formation to signs (from abstract to concrete). In visual information, the following levels appear: *structures – characteristics – frames – integrities – concrete visible elements*. In the icon by Rublev, different levels of integration are clearly seen in visible elements, from abstract relations to vital individuality of depicted objects. Abstract universals are materialized in generalized images and indefinite hints, obtain the character of living organisms, and appear as concrete iconic signs. Levels of organization are implemented in the relations between paradigmatics and syntagmatics, relying upon the process of narrative and discourse. In visual artworks, signs, texts, and semantic formations represent the implementations of semiotic systemities of different layers of culture. In the works of East Christian art, the stable signs of Christian visual culture are apparent. In their turn, they obtain the character of signs and are specified in the syntagmatics of artworks.

5. Sign form

In order to examine the semiotic systemity of visual art, it is necessary to introduce the idea of form. Semiotic scientists clearly distinguish forms and structures in the objects of art and culture (Levi-Strauss 1970). This distinction is fundamental. The form is the way of regulation of organism-environment interrelations and organization of different objects in human activity (Somov 2001). The form makes it possible to distinguish relations and structures, to represent and change them in thinking processes (Somov 1990). It is also the way of modeling and changing a situation. Being the way of modeling, it appears as a *sign form* (way of producing information) (Somov 2001, in press b). It is also possible to say

that the sign form represents sign interrelations, is based on the mechanisms of their formation (codes and structure interrelations), and unites these mechanisms into a single whole. The forms that we see and attribute to real objects are created on the fundament of codes. These forms include such denotations as: structural composition, boundaries, size ratios of objects as related to a human being, and physical properties of objects. On the other hand, the sign form implements intentions and goals (models of situation changes), becomes the way of modeling of transformations ‘situation – model – actions.’ Relation of form with objects, interpretants, and representamens generates various types of forms. *Three types of sign forms* are significant for the creation and perception of artworks: *denotative form*, representing mainly the modeling of real situations; *connotative form*, representing mainly the verbal basis related with sensor systemity and colored intentionally; and *organizing form* representing mainly sign interrelations. Due to the denotative form, we see and become acquainted with the objects of environment. Due to the connotative form, we feel emotional states and project moods and imaginary pictures on visual objects. Due to the organizing form, we feel the unity, clarity, and reliability of produced information. Sign forms of visual artworks can gravitate towards denotations, connotations, or organizations. In the three types of forms, *semiotic systemities* are distinguished: *systemity of denotations*, *systemity of connotations*, and *organizing systemity*. Each of them is organized by specific structures. These three types of forms, systemities, and structures are clearly seen in *The Trinity* by Rublev.

Systemities of denotations and connotations have a different character. *Systemity of denotations* represents models of situations — structures of causal relations and various conventionalities of modeled objects. In informational processes, the *denotations* appear as *logical systems of information*. In visual artworks, this appears, first of all, as ‘visual judgements’ (Arnheim 1974). This is why semiotic scientists regularly point that these artworks should be examined as logical information systems of a specific type (Gross 1973). Logical information systems form sequences. Sign chains are formed, which are analogous to the texts of articulate human speech. First, we see the situation as a whole, then we see its participants, and later on, characteristics of participants and secondary objects of entourage. Other sequences are possible, too. A sequence of this kind can be regarded as a structure of identification of situations. This model is supported when studying linguistic texts (Referovskaya 1989). ‘Texts and messages are realized across several codes’ (Heath 1981: 129). Correspondingly, *the systemity of denotations* is a sequence, which is fixed in different groups of representamens of identifications of a visual artwork. *Systemity of connotations* of artworks usually forms independent sign

structures. They may develop the branches of meanings, while the organization of general sequence is not obligatory. In such description, the term of text in the semiotics of visual art can be regarded as an aspect of sign form. In connotations, diffused meanings (semantic fields) are formed, which are relatively free with respect to denotations and text structures (Somov 2006). The organizing systemity and its structures also are relatively independent with respect to denotations.

6. Denotative form, its systemity and structures

Denotations of the icon have different levels and represent a metonymy. Viators marked by staffs and cloth denote Angels marked by wings and nimbi. Angels denote the Triunity and three hypostases of the Holy Trinity. Their figures are superimposed on a traditional heretical composition with the figure of Christ in the center. Like in earlier icon paintings, the central figure is interpreted as a more powerful and authoritative. But this is already the other Person: God the Father at the head of the Trinity. The cup given to the wanderers denotes the sacrifice of the lamb, which, in its turn, is the sacrifice of Christ. The house denotes the socium, the mountain, the ascent to the heavenly world, the Mambre oak, vital fundament and wisdom (S. Golubtsov 1972, 1981). *The main semantic system of denotations* is represented by the interrelations among the Persons of Trinity and the way of their denotation and representation. This needs to be represented semiotically, especially as the examiners of *The Holy Trinity* gave different answers to the question ‘Who is who?’ The system of Persons of the Holy Trinity is based on the episode of communication. The Angels are related by a common dialog where Two are blessing and One is agreeing to offer Himself in sacrifice. This system is expressed by sign formations (head inclinations, gestures, poses, color symbols, etc.). The majority of explorers identifies the Persons of Trinity by their poses and gestures. Poses and gestures of the central and right Angels are identical but differ from those of the left Angel. The Angel situated on the left is sitting straight and has a different position of hand. The two figures on the right incline similarly. They have similar actively expressed gestures. The Two are asking a question, exhorting, and blessing to offer a sacrifice. The third Person is agreeing. Lifted fingers of the left Angel correspond to the word ‘I agree’ in the language of medieval monks (S. Golubtsov 1972). Christ agrees to offer himself in sacrifice. In connection with this, an important fact is revealed. In the icon paintings of Byzantia, Georgia, and Russia, where Christ was painted with two Angels, he has the same hand gesture as the left Angel on the icon by

Rublev. That is, this was the episode of Christ agreement for sacrifice given to Angels. This points to the fact that the interpretation of the episode of Angels' visit to Abraham as the beginning of salvation of humankind was developed in theology independently on the doctrine of Trinity as three hypostases of God.

Significant denotations of gestures are expressed in developed visual characteristics. Blessing hand gestures of the central and right Angels are emphasized via the contrast with a light background of the table and thus become prominent. The hand of the left Angel seems to melt in the ochre background. This means that Christ's answer is natural and quiet. He inviolately 'agrees to accomplish the mundane mission of anguish and death for the salvation of humankind' (Demina 1963: 99). Therefore, the signs of gestures prove that Christ is painted on the left side. Some new arguments supporting this have been found recently by the explorers of *The Trinity*. In particular, the central Angel is more imperious and firm; the left Angel is gentler, as it is becoming to a son; the right leg of his throne is broken, which anticipate his martyr death. The semantic system (God the Son sitting on the left, God the Father, in the center, and the Holy Spirit, on the right) is developed in the denotations of background, as well. The inclination of silhouettes and heads of the central and right Angels are expressed metaphorically by inclined forms of mountains and Mambre oak. The building of the universe rises behind the left Angel, it is straight like Angel's silhouette and, according to some authors, resembles grave clothes of Christ. The mountain, which is the ancient sign of spiritual ascent, is painted on the right and denotes the Holy Spirit. The Mambre oak wood denoting the place of sacrifice and the tree of life gravitates to the center. The colors corresponding to Byzantine color system also contribute to the expression of the system of three hypostases of Trinity. Blue colors denote the spiritual sphere, dark cherry denotes the self-giving love, the brown color denotes the earth, and green denotes youth (S. Golubtsov 1972, 1981). This is why the green color covering the right Angel is interpreted as the characteristic of renovating and regenerating Holy Spirit. The combination of blue and brown colors, spiritual and earthy, expresses the theanthropic nature of Son of God. In general, the color of material world predominates in the figure of the left Angel. The central figure unites different natures in strong color contrasts.

Denotations get in visual artworks advanced systemity. In the Trinity, this systemity has received development into interrelations of basic semantically-important elements (figure 3). But systemity of denotations forms only a certain skeleton of artwork representamens. The basic sign formation of artwork is created by its connotative form.

Figure 3. *Interrelations of semantically significant elements. Representations of denotations are organized*

7. Connotative form, its systemity and structures

The connotations of artworks are free from text denotations, because the influence of text is not obligatory for code implementation in signs (Hall 1980). The connotations of the icon were affected by the possibility of

Figure 4. *Altar-fire*. The major configuration is materialized by a dark cherry color denoting self-giving love

implementation of multiple meanings. 'The work by Rublev, due to a limited number of selected figures and objects, requires an extremely responsible approach to the fulfillment of the task set to the icon painter in this restricted composition. Creative thought follows the way of deepening of the content, multiplication of richness of ideas, saturation of symbols and technical methods by diverse meanings' (N. Golubtsov 1960: 35). The nucleus of icon meanings was to be strengthened by hidden con-

Figure 5. *Three configurations resembling the altar fire*

notations. Earlier, I have demonstrated some of these connotations when analyzing the levels of sign systems in visual art (Somov 2006). They will be examined in details below. The *sacrifice* is a leading connotation of sign systemity of the icon. The depicted system itself is a prototype of future sacrifice. Above the cup, the icon painter depicted the flame in the configurations of Angels' clothes (figures 4, 5, and 6). It is the sign of sacrifice and self-giving love, which is the major idea of Christianity. The

Figure 6. *Contours of altar fire flowing into those of smoke*

skyward altar fire is a predominating expressive configuration of composition and assigns an emotional character to its perception. The development of the flame upwards is strengthened by the configurations resembling swirls of smoke (figure 7). Representations of flame occupy a central position in the composition and are the most active by color. Color contrast is created inside the flame. The dark cherry color of chiton surrounds the azure color of the cloak. In the Byzantine sign system, the

Figure 7. *Forms of Angels' figures and tree resembling flames and swirls of smoke*

dark cherry color represented the sign of self-giving love, while the azure one symbolized spiritual and intellectual nature (S. Golubtsov 1981). This color combination forms a metonymy: the mind is directed by feelings, the spiritual nature is born and evolves in the substance of superior love. Rublev expressed visually and metaphorically the ideas developed by Christian philosophers.

Figure 8. *Cup of sacrifice and its large repeating configuration. Symbols of sacrifice and integrity of the universe*

The unity also is expressed by the cup (Alpatov 1972; S. Golubtsov 1981). These investigators have noted that, being the symbol of unity, it was placed in the center. This central position of the cup is reinforced by the system of interrelations of Angels' faces, hands, and feet, which was demonstrated in figure 2. A large ascending configuration develops, resembling a large cup (figures 8 and 9). An even larger configuration

Figure 9. *Contours of large cup of sacrifice in the general composition. Modification of the cup represented in figure 8*

Figure 10. *Three configurations of sacrifice cup denoting the triunity of the world and universality of the sacrifice*

resembles an inverted cup (figure 10). All of the three cups are framed by irregular contours and hence point to Sangraal with the pouring blood of Christ. In general, the three cups actively organize the image field and create sign representation: the unity of the universe is based on tri-personality.

Figure 11. *Masque of a bear as a hidden sign of defeated shamanism of heathen peoples*

Christian symbols seem to be superimposed over heretical and heathen ones. To use an old sign as a basis for the new one meant to overcome past superstitions. Building of sanctuary of new religion on the place of old ones, involvement of heathen images in the signs of Christian motives, and incorporation of symbols of regions into state symbolism — all of this can be seen on wall reliefs of the churches of Vladimir-Suzdal

Figure 12. *Contours of bear in general active configurations. Color modification of the sign represented in figure 11*

Princedom of the twelfth century. Such concepts of magic force of signs became especially important in Moscow Princedom of the period of Rublev. Historical situation favored this. In particular, in 1395, Tamerlane approached to Moscow with a huge army. According to the legend, the city was saved by Our Lady of Vladimir, envisioned in the conqueror's dream. In the art of that period, miraculous forces and magic signs

Figure 13. *Contours forming a monumental sign of beast. Contours are formed by active straight and rectified lines of the image*

became especially important (signs of nimbi and protection of the Virgin, triads of the Holy Trinity, structures of the vivifying Cross, etc.). Magic concepts were developed in the composition of *The Trinity* by Rublev, as well. The composition was as though superposed over the heretical composition, which included the representation of Christ and two Angels. However, in addition, it was underlain by an important heathen symbol,

Figure 14. *Contours resembling a sorrow face. Some color configurations with light blue and blue tones resemble large tears*

which should be examined in a more detailed way. Missionary work was an important activity of church in the fourteenth century. Due to the deeds of Bishop Stephan, Christianity was preached to the tribes populating the forests in the basins of the Vychegda, North Dvina, and Kama rivers, and the Russian language was spread. The mission of St. Stephan

Figure 15. *Contours resembling a sorrowful face of spirit*

preceded the deeds of St. Sergius and was regarded as a great victory of the church. Besides, St. Stephan under the legend was the friend of St. Sergius and also communicated with him by telepathy. This is supported by their hagiography written by their contemporary, monk Epiphanius the Wise. Church deeds in the field of christening heathen peoples needed to be reflected in the sign systems of a great artwork. The interrelation

Figure 16. *Contours resembling a face of spirit. His eyes are formed by glimpses among Angels' wings and nimbi*

of *The Trinity* by Rublev with the mission of St. Stephan is noticeable in its similarity to the composition of so-called *Trinity of Zyryan*, which was brought by St. Stephan to the lands of *zyryane* tribes. Historical facts point out that the presence of heathen signs in the composition of *The Trinity* is possible. The most important cult of *komi-zyryane* tribes

Figure 17. *Contours resembling noble features*

known since the Stone Age was that of the bear (Gemuev 2000). In their ceremonies, shamans wore bear masques, which can be seen in the museums of Ural cities. Let us add that the present emblem of the city of Perm (former residence of St. Stephan) represents a bear carrying the Gospel in gold setting on its back and the cross above the beast. This emblem was adopted in the eighteenth century and symbolized the christening of a

Figure 18. *Circular movement denoting circulation of energies and Space*

pagan land where the carnivore animal was worshiped. This is why the *connotation of the bear head* is not unexpected (figures 11, 12).

The representation of beast masque was developed in other connotations of theroid creatures and spirits (figures 13, 14, 15, 16, 17). Due to this, sorrowful images and moods are formed, emotionally complementing the main sense of the episode.

Figure 19. *Dashed lines forming the contours of Angels' figures and major lines of folds denoting descending light fluxes*

The connotation of unity is expressed by gentle circular contours and mutual subordination of Angels. This creates 'inexpressible grace of mutual inclinations, silence, voicelessness, still dialog, and eternal unity of celestial spheres' (Florensky 1989: 52). Circular motion is born in mutually interflowing lines (figure 18). According to Byzantine ideas, this

Figure 20. *Contours of Byzantine cherubim*

circular motion denoted identity in movements and transformations (Pseudo-Dionysius Areopagite 1962). As an even more ancient sign tracing back to Vedantic Mandala, the circular motion denoted the universe and energy flows. The idea of energies was developed in the other connotation. *The connotation of divine energy of light* appears in different characteristics of the icon. White and yellow tones predominate in the color

Figure 21. *Contours of Byzantine four-winged angel (seraphim)*

gamma; bright white blinks are introduced. The major color gamma and created unusual luminous effects are regarded as the incarnation of the idea of Byzantine theologian Grigorius Palama of vivifying energy of light (Onasch 1962, 1988). This statement can be supported by some picture characteristics — dashed contour-organizing lines. They resemble light flows penetrating the world (figure 19).

Figure 22. *Contours denoting lifted wings of the central Angel. The contours are marked by color and lines of the background and are proportionally comparable with Angel's figure*

Connotations of angels and spirits are expressed by different means and become complicated. Active contours of figures of the left and right Angels, in combination with the head and nimbus of the central figure resemble a well recognized Byzantine sign of a cherubim represented as head and wings (figures 20, 21). The most well-known images of this kind

Figure 23. *Contours denoting hanged wings of the central Angel. The contours are marked by the boundaries of color configurations and active lines of clothes of other Angels*

are painted on the dome vaults of St. Sophia Cathedral in Constantinopolis. Connotations of wings repeat the picture of Angels' figures (figures 22, 23). These connotations are strengthened by the effect of symmetry of wings and figure contours (figure 24). An important role of Byzantine signs of angels in visual culture is supported by their frequent presence in holy books (figures 25, 26). Later on, these signs were significantly

Figure 24. *Wings of a Byzantine angel in the system of mirror symmetry. The connotation perfectly relates the image with a traditional sign of cherubim's head and wings*

developed in architectural forms and frescos. In particular, the largest monastery of Russian North, Kirillo-Belozerskii, was built as the imitation of Troitse-Sergiev one.

Symbolically significant signs of the Trinity Cathedral (integral module, structure of plan, and major sections) were developed in the architec-

Figure 25. Miniature of a Greek manuscript, 'The Holy Trinity' (the 1130s, *The Homilium of Jakob of Kockinobath*. Library of Vatican, Rome)

ture of its Cathedral of Assumption built in 1497 (Podyapolsky 1988: 313). Angels' wings of *The Trinity* by Rublev became the connotation of architectural motive of aperture framing in this cathedral. Byzantine signs of cherubim became a major sign system of portals and aperture framings in the architecture of churches, tower-chambers, and palaces of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries (Grabarand fon Eding 1912; figures 27, 28). Later on, in the eighteenth century, they were used in the architecture of Russian Baroque style. At the icon, the connotations of Angels' wings complement their denotations (figure 29), are developed in the systems of lines and contours of the mountain, silhouettes of Angels' figures and clothes (figure 30). Dashed lines inside these lines and contours produce the impression of wing flutter and rustle (figure 31). A mystic feeling of

Figure 26. Miniature of Greek manuscript of the New Testament, 'Paternity' (late twelfth century, National Library of Vienna)

the presence of bodiless creatures is reinforced by *faces-masques* showing through the contours of Angels' figures (figures 32, 33, and 34).

The connotations relating the icon with traditional signs of the Moscow Church and its architectural centers were developed in the system of keel- and heart-shaped contours (figure 35). These heart-shaped configurations also are developed in the connotations of major sense of the icon, or sense of love, forming the general picture of Angels' figures and clothes (figures 36, 37). Keel-shaped configurations of *The Trinity* repeat the keel-shaped configurations of decorative arched elements of the main church of Troitse-Sergiev monastery (figure 38) and other churches of Moscow Princedom. One of them is supposed to have been designed by Rublev simultaneously with the creation of *The Trinity* (figure 39) (Laz-

Figure 27. *Church of the Savior, Rostov-the-Great. 1675. Entrance to the altar. The sign of two-winged spirit (cherubim) protects the boundary of altar space*

Figure 28. *Wall paintings in the Church of Conception of the Yakovlevskii Monastery, Rostov-the-Great. Late seventeenth century. Signs of angels on ceiling and vaults form mirror symmetries in two directions*

Figure 29. *Identical configuration of similar color forming the signs of angels' wings*

arev 1997). In general, these connotations produced the impression of image attribution to the forms of spiritual center of the Trinity and orthodox Christianity, which were well known by spectators. The icons continued architecture of cathedrals in Russian religious art (Trubetskoi 2003 [1916]).

Figure 30. *Configurations of angels' wings in basic contours and lines. The world populated with heavenly spirits*

The connotations of the icon as a whole form rich indefinite visual meanings that are extremely important for visual art (Panofsky 1983 [1955]); semantic fields without any definite designates are created (Somov 2006). This produces the feeling of light rustles, tremor of invisible living beings, presence of external forces, flowing energies, water murmur,

Figure 31. *Configurations of angels' wings partitioned by internal patterns. Connotation of fluttering wings*

transparent multi-layered universe, and the penetration of spiritual natures into the physical world.

As a whole, connotations of *The Trinity* also designate three beginnings: Belief, Hope, and Love. As the researchers of *St. Trinity* specify, Rublev proceeded from the doctrine of Ioann Lestvichnik, which bound

Figure 32. *Configurations of contours and identical color as representamens of connotations. Faces-masques*

Belief to the Way by a direct line, Hope with Light, Love with circular movements and fluidity energy (Lazarev 1997). This triad unites three distinctive visual attributes of the icon — strict direct lines of crosiers and their directions, light flows of all fields of the image, intersubordination and circular fluidity of lines.

Figure 33. *Faces-masques. The connotation is formed by active contours*

8. Organizing form, its systemity and structures

This form unites the structures organizing the interrelations of representamens. The signals tend to be included in representamens of denotations and connotations. This is why the structures organizing the signals of visual artworks tend to become characteristics and differences — identities,

Figure 34. *Faces-masques. The connotation is formed by continued active lines*

which form the representamens of denotations and connotations and simultaneously are spread to different relations and elements. In the icon by Rublev, structural organization of signals involves all basic relations and elements: color configurations, contours, axes, centers, differences, and identities by differential characteristics. The structures are quite apparent on the icon. The basic triadic structure of the icon represents the

Figure 35. *Keel- and heart-shaped configurations resembling the most important cathedrals of Moscow Princedom and, most of all, Cathedral of the Holy Trinity in the Troitse-Sergiev Monastery*

tripersonality. The triad of wanderers is a metonymy of the triad of Angels, while the latter is a metonymy of the triad of God hypostases. Each of these triads is developed in triadic sign systems: the wanderers are marked by the triad of staffs interrelated with the triad of sights passing

Figure 36. *Heart-shaped configurations of Angels' figures and general composition of the image*

through the cup (figure 2). The triad of Angels is expressed by the system of nimbi and wings; three hypostases of God, by the system: chambers – oakery – heavenly world.

Triadic structures of *The Trinity*, together with other structures, were developed in the layer of signals and interrelated in a complex way with

Figure 37. *Configuration of heart in contours and color configurations of Angels' figures*

the semantics of the icon. Let us examine some typical relation-organizing structures.

Color ratios are organized by specific structures. Ochre tones with pinkish and greenish tints predominate. Greenish tints of the right lower part of the icon are equilibrated by pinkish tints in the upper right part. Dom-

Figure 38. *The Cathedral of the Holy Trinity of the Troitse-Sergiev Monastery (1422) as architectural context of 'The Holy Trinity' by Rublev*

inating brownish-pinkish colors of the figure of the left Angel are equilibrated by greenish tints of the upper and lower left part.

Color sections are integer structures. Dark (brown and cherry-brown) configurations organize the central part of the icon; light sections are yellow-white, yellowish, and ochre. Yellow-white fragments denote a divine light around the sacrifice. The triad of nimbi corresponds to the triad of light elements of the lower part: table plane and two pediments. These light configurations of the lower part are likened to Angels' heads and figures. The holy triad is represented by color at Trinity feet. Two tints of light color, pinkish and greenish tones also form a mirror symmetry (from left to right and downwards) and evenly fill the image space. The configurations of ochre color are spread in a symmetrical and even way (wings, pediments, and thrones).

Relations of allocation and sizes of basic elements are organized by proportions. This organization is based on triangle (figure 40), which was the sign of Trinity in Mediaeval epoch (Gika 1937; Barbyshev and Somov 1990). The triangle slightly deviates from the equilateral one. As a result, the systemity of proportions is formed in the interrelation with the major

Figure 39. *The cathedral of St. Andronich Monastery, Moscow (1425), which is supposed to be painted by Rublev. The composition is based on a rhythmic development of heart-shaped arched elements*

Figure 40. *Magic triangles of 'The Trinity'*

Figure 41. *Magic triangles and basic proportions*

field of image (figures 41, 42, 43). *Relations of element allocation* are organized by their subordination to organizing lines. Like proportions, lines are organizing structures, which correspond to the definition of structure as principle of construction and way of linking the interrelations of elements of the whole. The active structure of organizing focus points subordinates the lines and points of the image (figure 44). This strengthens an important connotation of descending light flows, which has been demonstrated earlier in figure 19. Explorers of *The Trinity* pointed to a

Figure 42. *Basic proportions*

specific phenomenon — the lasting perception of lines by a spectator, their special importance in general effect of the icon. This importance of lines is partly explained by their involvement in connotations. However, the lines of *The Trinity* also possess a developed structure as elements-signals (figures 45, 46). A specific structure is intrinsic to large configurations formed by the areas of homogeneous color and active contours (figures 47, 48). In

Figure 43. *Basic proportions*

the lower part, the ornamental composition of triangles is formed. These elements denote the triadic character and brutality of earth and produce a rhythmic structure. Materialized triangles of the lower part are related with hidden magic triangles shown in figure 40. There is a gradual transition from triangle elements of the bottom to larger triangles of the middle part and then, to the roundings and circles of the top. Wings and nimbi

Figure 44. *Rays beginning in the upper focus points as a structure forming composition lines and points*

Figure 45. *Organizing lines*

seem to grow from the triangle fundament of the universe. The rhythm of composition development in the ascending direction is strengthened by the system of elements, subordinated to the lines beginning in the lower focus point (figure 49). This ascending dispersion of elements is sustained by the allocation of active light elements of Angels' faces and nimbi (figure 50) and rhythmic ascending change of sign representamens (figure

Figure 46. *Organizing lines relating the most significant signals and signs of Angels' heads and nimbi*

51). The opposition of triangle elements and circles of the Trinity is reinforced by the system of mutual allocation of two triangle vertexes (figure 52). Sharp triangle folds are opposed to the circles of nimbi denoting the contrast between divine and evil forces. Relations and elements of image field are organized by the system of partitions: upper, middle, and lower

Figure 47. *Triangle ornamentation of the lower part of the composition*

(figure 53). Each partition is divided in three. The reflection of triads in the lower field, which is symmetrical to the upper part, denotes the universality of triadic structure of the world. Horizontal partitions are expressed by the boundaries of color configurations and lines. The proportions of these layers are close to the golden section, which promotes their best identification.

Figure 48. *Triangle and trapeziform configurations of the lower part of composition and their development in the top part*

Like in other works of visual art, *mirror symmetries* reinforce the structural organization of signals. In *The Trinity*, these symmetries seem to have their own semantics. Around the main axis, spiroid S-shaped movements are developed, forming the rotary symmetry (figure 54), Wanderers' staffs also are axes of symmetry of spiroid movements (figure 55).

Figure 49. *Spreading elements of composition*

Staffs denote ways; therefore, spiroid development follows three ways. It is probable that Rublev purposely tried to express the theological ideas of spiritual ascent. Rotary symmetries developed around the axes of staffs complement general mirror and rotary symmetries. One of them is repre-

Figure 50. *Triads of configurations of ochre color*

sented at figure 56. The main function of these symmetries in visual art is structural organization of signals. In the icon by Rublev, the symmetries obtain a specific semantics in the context of universe representation. Parts of the image produce an impression of mutually reflecting mirrors. According to ancient mystic concepts, mirrors are the boundaries of parallel worlds.

Figure 51. *Triads of the lightest elements of composition*

In general, organizing structures form the general structure of composition. The explorers of the icon noted: 'Preserving entirely its centric character and possessing the equilibrium of masses, the icon simultaneously has a symphonic richness of rhythms' (Lazarev 1989: 108).

Figure 52. *Structures of contrast characteristics*

9. Sign systems of elements and details

Some elements and details of visual artworks represent sign systems. Characteristics of contours, lines, and configurations (convexity, concavity, S-shape, mild roundings, active points and zones of contour break, straight, curvilinear, and broken fragments, sharp and obtuse angles of

Figure 53. *Structural partitioning of composition field*

turnings, and smoothed or angled parts — triangle or trapeziform ones) are active signals. They evolve to connotative integrities. The image is organized by the contrast of smoothed and triangle-trapeziform configurations and that of lines: smooth, broken, and straight. These contrasts visually organize the plane of image. They also represent a semantic opposition. Smooth and rounded configurations and lines and circles of

Figure 54. *Symmetrical S-shaped configurations and lines. The vertical axis of composition represents the axis of rotation*

nimbi denoting the divine nature, harmony, and concord, are opposed to sharp thorny contours, sharp-angled nodes of converging lines, arrow-like straight contours denoting tension, hostility, martial forces, and, probably, evil. The first group dominates over the second. The configurations with arrow-like triangle silhouettes inside form the fields of tension (figure

Figure 55. *Symmetrical S-shaped configurations and lines around staffs*

57). Rublev aggravated and schematized geometric characteristics of cloth folds. In the figure of the left Angel, fold spikes have the earth color with purple tint in the lower part and cut into the pediment and throne leg. The arrows of blue fluttering cloth folds of the right Angels are directed even sharper. The silhouettes of these folds resemble arrows and

Figure 56. *Mirror symmetry of the composition*

lightning. The silhouettes of this kind can be seen in the icons of twelfth to fourteenth centuries representing St. George striking a serpent. They can be interpreted as heavenly forces fighting against the evil, or 'host of Christ.' It is natural that the tracery of the lower folds of Angels' clothes in *The Trinity* by Rublev was studied and modified in the frescos

Figure 57. *Sharp dissected configurations of folds of Angels' clothes resembling those of the icons of St. George killing a serpent*

of the fifteenth century by Dionysius and his disciples (Laurina 1989). The main folds of azure chiton of the central Angel also are subordinated to a strained and rigorous emotional state. The folds are organized as a system of sharp triangle and trapeziform configurations and contours. They reinforce the certitude and power of the central figure of God the

Figure 58. *Folds-faces. The connotation is formed by the most active contours of folds of clothes of the central Angel*

Father and are a strong mean of emotion intensification. Triangle silhouettes resembling strict and severe faces are noticeable in the contours of folds (figures 58, 59, 60). These face-shaped folds hidden in the contours of clothes are a traditional technique of Byzantine visual art. Rublev used this method in order to develop basic meanings of the icon. Sharp straight, arrow-like, and triangular contours impart not only severity

Figure 59. *Folds-faces. The connotation is created by form-generating lines of cloth folds*

but the features of anguish and sorrow to 'folds-faces.' The allocation of these faces is quite natural. They are found in the azure (non-material) sphere, as though ascending to God the Father and being under his protection, and simultaneously soar over the cup. According to ancient ideas, the cup brought peace and soul seclusion. In general, 'folds-faces' denote the souls devoted to the God and self-sacrifice. Judging from a severe and

Figure 60. *Folds-faces*. The connotation is formed by general silhouettes of cloth folds

suffering appearance, they denote saint elders and martyrs following the way of the Savior.

Note

1. Quotations from Laurina (1989), S. Golubtsov (1981), N. Golubtsov (1960), Alpatov (1972), Florensky (1989), Demina (1963), and Lazarev (1989) have been translated from Russian by the author.

References

- Alpatov, Mikhail V. (1972). *Andrey Rublev*. Moscow: Iskusstvo.
- (1974). *Kraski drevnerusskoy ikonopisi* [The colors of old Russian iconography]. Moscow: Iskusstvo.
- Altman, Rick (1992). The material heterogeneity of recorded sound. In *Sound Theory, Sound Practice*, Rick Altman (ed.), 15–31. New York: Routledge.
- Arnheim, Rudolf (1974). *Art and Visual Perception: A Psychology of the Creative Eye*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press.
- Barbyshev, Eugeny N. and Somov, Georgij Yu. (1990). Formoobrazuyushie struktury i arkhitekturnaya forma [The form-making structures and the architectural form]. *Architecture of USSA* 2, 8–14.
- Chandler, Daniel (1994). *Semiotics for Beginners*. Available online at <http://www.aber.ac.uk/media/Documents/S4B/semiotic.html>.
- Cherry, Colin (1952). The communication of information. *American Scientist* 40 (4), 640–664.
- (1966). *On Human Communication*, 2nd ed. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Demina, Natalya A. (1963). *Troitca Andrey Rubleva* [The Trinity of Andrey Rublev]. Moscow: Nauka.
- Deregowski, Jan B. (1980). *Illusions, Patterns, and Pictures: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*. New York: Academic Press.
- Eco, Umberto (1976). *A Theory of Semiotics*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Fiske, John (1989). Codes. In *International Encyclopedia of Communications*, vol. 1, 312–316. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Florensky, Pavel A. (1989). Troitse-Sergieva Lavra i Rossiya [The Troitse-Sergieva Lavra and Russia]. In *Troitsa Andrey Rubleva* [The Trinity of Andrey Rublev], Gerold I. Vzdornov (ed.), 52–53. Moscow: Iskusstvo.
- Gemuev, Ismail N. (ed.) (2000). *Narody Sibiri: istoriya i kul'tura. Medved' v drevnih i sovremennih kul'turah Sibiri* [The peoples of Siberia: A history and culture. A bear in ancient and modern cultures of Siberia]. Novosibirsk: IAET SO RAN [Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography Russian Academy of Science, Siberian department].
- Gika, Matila (1937). *Estetika proporsiy v prirode i iskusstve* [The aesthetics of proportions in the nature and in the art]. Moscow: Academy of Architecture.
- Golubtsov, Nikolai A. (1960). Presyataya Troitsa I domostroitel'stvo (Ob ikone inoka Andrey Rubleva) [The Holy Trinity and housebuilding (On the icon of Holy Trinity by Andrey Rublev)]. *Journal of Moscow Patriarchate* 7, 32–40.
- Golubtsov, Sergius (1972). Ikona jivonachal'noy Troitsy [The icon of live-creating Trinity]. *Journal of Moscow Patriarchate* 7, 69–76.
- (1981). Voplosh'enie bogoslovskih idey v tvorchestve prepodobnogo Andrey Rubleva [The realization of theological ideas in creative works of Andrey Rublev]. *Bogoslovskie trudy* 22, 20–40.
- Grabar, Igor E. and Eding, Boris fon (1912). *Russkie goroda — rassadniki iskusstva: Rostov Veliky, Uglich* [The Russian towns — nurseries of Art: Rostov Veliky, Uglich]. Moscow: Knebel.
- Gross, Larry (1973). Art as the communication of competence. *Social Science Information* 12, 115–141.
- Hall, Stuart (1980). Encoding/decoding. In *Culture, Media, Language: Working Papers in Cultural Studies 1972–1979*, Stuart Hall et al. (eds.), 128–138. London: Hutchinson.
- Heath, Stephen (1981). Metz's semiology: A short glossary. In *Cinema and Semiotics* (= Screen Reader 2), Mick Eaton (ed.), 125–137. London: Society for Education in Film and Television.

- Jakobson, Roman (1971). Language in relation to other communication systems. In *Selected Writings*, Roman Jakobson (ed.), vol. 2, 570–579. Mouton: The Hague.
- Lazarev, Viktor N. (1989). Russkaya srednevekovaya zhivopis' [Medieval Russian art]. In *Troitsa Andrey Rubleva* [The Trinity of Andrey Rublev], Gerold I. Vzdornov (ed.), 104–110. Moscow: Iskusstvo.
- (1997). *The Russian Icon: From Its Origins to the Sixteenth Century*, Gerold I. Vzdornov (ed.). Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press.
- Laurina, Vera K. (1989). Dionisii i iskusstvo Moskvy XV–XVI stoletii [Dionysius and art of Moscow fifteenth–sixteenth centuries]. In *Drevnerusskoe iskusstvo* [Old Russian art], Gennadiy V. Popov (ed.), 84–112. Moscow: Nauka.
- Lemke, Jay L. (1983). Thematic analysis: systems, structures, and strategies. *Recherches Semiotiques / Semiotic Inquiry* 3, 159–187.
- Levi-Strauss, Claude (1970). *Anthropologie Structurale*. Paris: Deux Plon.
- Morris, Charles W. (1971). *Writings on the General Theory of Signs*. Paris: Mouton.
- Onasch, Konrad (1962). *Das Problem des Lichtes in der Ikonmalerei Andrej Rublevs. Zur 600-Jahrfeier des grossen russischen Malers*, vol. 28. Berlin: Berliner byzantinische Arbeiten.
- (1988). Das Gedankenmodell des byzantisch-slawischen Kirchenbaus. In *Tausend Jahre Christentum in Russland*, Karl Christian Felmy et al. (eds.), 539–543. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht.
- Panofsky, Erwin (1983 [1955]). *Meaning in the Visual Arts*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Podyapolsky, Sergey S. (1988). Kamennoe zodchestvo Kirillo-Belozerskogo monastyrya v ego otnoshenii k stroitel'stvu Troitse-Sergievskogo monastyrya [The masonry architecture of Kirillo-Belozersky monastery in relation to building the Troitse-Sergiev monastery]. In *Drevnerusskoe iskusstvo: khudozhestvennaya kul'tura x — pervoy poloviny xiii v.* [Old Russian art: The artistic culture x — the early half of the thirteenth century], Gennadiy V. Popov (ed.), 310–319. Moscow: Nauka.
- Prieto, Luis (1964). *Principes de noologie. Fondements de la Theorie fonctionnelle du signifie*. The Hague: Mouton.
- Pseudo-Dionysius Areopagite (1962). *Pamyatniki mirovoy esteticheskoy mysli* [Monuments of the world aesthetic idea], Mikhail F. Ovsyannikov (ed.), vol. 1. Moscow: Academy of Art USSA.
- Raushenbah, Boris V. (1975). *Prostranstvennie postroeniya v drevnerusskoy zhivopisi* [Spatial constructions in the old Russian art]. Moscow: Nauka.
- (1994). *Geometriya kartiny i zritel'noe vospriyatie* [The geometry of painting and visual perception]. Moscow: Interpracs.
- Referovskaya, Elizaveta A. (1989). *Kommunikativnaya struktura teksta* [The communicative structure of the text]. Leningrad: Nauka.
- Sapir, Edward (1930). Totality. *Language Monograph* 6, 6–28.
- Sebeok, Thomas A. (1999). The sign science and the life science. *Applied Semiotics / Semiotique Appliquée* 6–7, 1–8.
- Sharov, Alexey A. (1999). The origin and evolution of signs. *Semiotica* 127, 521–535.
- Somjen, George (1972). *Sensory Coding in the Mammalian Nervous System*. New York: Meredith.
- Somov, Georgij Yu. (1985a). Emotsional'noe vozdeystvie arkhitekturnoy sredi i eyo organizatsiya [Emotional effect of architectural environment and its organization]. In *Arkhitektura i emotsional'nyi mir cheloveka* [Architecture and emotional world of a person], G. B. Zabelshanskii (ed.), 82–149. Moscow: Stroiizdat.
- (1985b). Organizatsiya esteticheskoi znachimoy arkhitekturnoy formi [The organization of esthetically significant architectural form]. In *Arkhitektura i emotsional'nyi mir cheloveka*

- [Architecture and emotional world of a person], G. B. Zabelshanskii (ed.), 174–201. Moscow: Stroizdat.
- (1990). Problemy teorii arkhitekturnoy formy [Problems of the theory of architectural form]. In *Forma v arkhitekture* (Form in architecture), Alexander G. Rappaport and Georgij Yu Somov (eds.), 164–334. Moscow: Stroizdat.
- (2001). Semiotics of architecture and architecture of semiotics. *Semiotiche Berichte* 1–4, 339–352.
- (2005). Semiotic systems of works of visual art: Signs, connotations, signals. *Semiotica* 157 (1/4), 1–34.
- (2006). Connotations in semiotic systems of visual art (by the example of works by M. A. Vrubel). *Semiotica* 158 (1/4), 147–212.
- (in press a). Structures, signs, and mental activity. *S-European Journal for Semiotic Studies*.
- (in press b). Semiotic objects in regulation models. *S-European Journal for Semiotic Studies*.
- Sonesson, Göran (1989). *Pictorial Concepts*. Lund: Lund University Press.
- (1993). Pictorial semiotics, Gestalt psychology, and the ecology of perception. Review of Saint-Martin, Fernande, La théorie de la Gestalt et l'art visuel. *Semiotica* 99 (3/4), 319–399.
- Titz, Alexey A. (1994). Arhitektura moskovskogo knyazhestva [The architecture of Moscow principedom]. In *Istoriia russkoi arkhitektury* [The history of the Russian architecture], Yurii S. Ushakov and Tatyana A. Slavina (eds.), 93–98. Moscow: Stroizdat.
- Trubetskoi, Eugeny N. (2003 [1916]). *Русская иконопись. Умозрение в красках. Вопрос о смысле жизни в древнерусской религиозной живописи* [Russian icon painting. Colourful contemplation. Question of the meaning of life in early Russian religious painting]. Moscow: Belyi Gorod.
- Vzdornov, Gerold I. (1989). From compiler. In *Troitca Andreya Rubleva* [The Trinity of Andrey Rublev], 5–14. Moscow: Iskusstvo.
- Uspensky, Boris A. (1976). *The Semiotics of the Russian Icon* (= Semiotics of Art 3), Stephen Rudy (ed.). Lisse: Peter de Ridder Press.

Georgij Yu. Somov (b. 1946) is an Associate Professor at Moscow State Building University <georgij.somov@gmail.com>, home page: gsomov.com. His research interests include theory of architecture and urban design, semiotics of architecture and visual art, and theoretical semiotics. His recent publications include ‘System-forming processes in the semiotic studies of architecture’ (2002); ‘Conviviality problem in the structure of semiotic objects’ (2003); ‘Semiotic systems of works of visual art: Signs, connotations, signals’ (2005); and ‘Connotations in semiotic systems of visual art (by the example of works by M. A. Vrubel)’ (2006).